

Exploring The Rich Handicraft Traditions of North-East India: A Case Study on The Handicraft of Assam

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The handicraft traditions of North-East India, particularly Assam, are deeply rooted in the cultural heritage of the region. Assam is renowned for its diverse crafts, including Assam silk, Eri silk, cane, bamboo crafts, and black pottery. Manipur excels in weaving and bamboo crafts, while Nagaland is known for its integrated Naga shawls with unique designs. Meghalaya stands out for its artistic textile weaving and wood carving, along with its unique craft of pineapple fiber articles. Manipur's handicraft industry includes stone carving, block printing, hand embroidery, cloth weaving, wood carving, and black pottery. The preservation of these traditional handicrafts faces challenges such as competition from mass-produced goods and financial constraints. However, platforms like iTokri have enabled local artisans to showcase their crafts to a broader audience. Today, artisans are exporting and exhibiting their creations globally, contributing significantly to the socio-economic development of the region. The rich artistic history of North-East India is reflected in its handicrafts, which showcase the distinctive customs and creativity of its indigenous tribes. Each state in the region has a vibrant craft tradition that manifests in various products reflecting the talent and skill of its artisans. From carpet making to woodcarvings, from handloom weaving to jewelry making, the crafts of North-East India encompass a wide array of art forms that are integral to the cultural identity and economic growth of the region. The study focuses on exploring the rich handicraft traditions of North-East India, with a case study on the handicraft of Assam, which reveals the diverse and vibrant craft heritage of the region.

Keywords: Handicrafts, Culture, Crafts, Assam, Heritage, North East India.